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FACTORIAL STUDY OF MATERIAL AND PROCESS PARAMETERS ON FIRE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOOL AND WHEAT GLUTEN COMPOSITES

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Wool and Gluten for Composites?

• Wool

Wool fibre

Extrusion

Mechanical test

V-0

Char formation

FR wool

• Wheat Gluten

Gluten powder

Compression moulding

Samples

Char formation

Das et al. J Clean Prod, 222(10) 2019

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Yes, Possible Manufacturing

- Manufacturing**

Mixing

Granules

Pressed samples

Factorial Design of Experiments

Sample	A. Moulding Temperature (°C)	B. Glycerol (wt.%)	Interaction factor A x B	D. Wool fibre (wt.%)	Interaction factor A x D	Interaction factor B x D
L1	140	20	1	20	1	1
L2	140	20	1	30	2	2
L3	140	30	2	20	1	2
L4	140	30	2	30	2	1
L5	160	20	2	20	2	1
L6	160	20	2	30	1	2
L7	160	30	1	20	2	2
L8	160	30	1	30	1	1

Yes, Good Performance

• Fire resistant

Self Extinguishment

• Mechanical

Sample	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile stress (MPa)	Tensile Strain (%)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural Stress (MPa)
Neat Gluten	3.97	16.0	0.21	3.5	28.7
Wool/Gluten composite	2.95	21.1	1.19	2.22	39.8

